

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D8.4

Data Management Plan

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Among natural hazards, earthquakes lead to the highest number fatalities and, after severe storms, cause the second highest annual economic losses. This is not only true worldwide, but also for the European continent.

TURNkey aims to make significant advances in the fields of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) and the Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE), particularly when applying these systems in practice in Europe. The project will develop a flexible, extendable, robust and easy-to-use OEF/EEW/RRE system based on low-cost-multi-sensor units and a cloud-based computer platform, which can be distributed as a fully-operational TURNkey product to public authorities (including search and rescue teams) and private companies (including operators of critical infrastructure). These developments will contribute to improved seismic resilience before, during and after a damaging earthquake and hence a reduction in losses.

The project's outcomes will be demonstrated in six European Testbeds (TBs) with different hazard, vulnerability and exposure characteristics, spatial extents and monitoring networks as well as in two roaming TBs, one based on crowdsourcing and one for temporary installations. The six geographically-focused TBs are: the city of Bucharest (Romania), the Pyrenees mountain range (France), the towns of Hveragerdi and Husavik (Iceland), the cities of Patras and Aigio (Greece), the maritime port of Gioia Tauro (Southern Italy), and the Groningen Province (Netherlands), which is affected by induced seismicity.

The TURNkey consortium comprises a strong multi-disciplinary team of experts (geophysicists, seismologists, geologists, engineers, disaster risk managers, sociologists, information technologists and computer programmers) from 21 partner institutions in 10 European countries. The TURNkey project will be supported by major public and private stakeholders in the six geographically-focused TBs and will be advised and reviewed by a group of international experts. TURNkey will build on previous and ongoing projects funded by the European Commission (EC) and national agencies that address topics related to OEF, EEW and RRE.

2 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

This document contains the second version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the TURNkey project, which has been elaborated in WP8 and reviewed by the Executive Board. The goal of this document is to aid the TURNkey project consortium to meet their responsibilities regarding research data quality, sharing and security through the provision of a DMP in accordance with the Horizon2020 Guidelines on Open Access.

DMPs are a key element of good data management. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon 2020 project. As part of making research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR), a DMP includes information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project;
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated;
- which methodology and standards will be applied;
- whether data will be shared/made open access; and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

The DMP needs to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- new data;
- changes in consortium policies (e.g., new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent); and
- changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g., new consortium members joining or old members leaving).

This second version of the DMP is now updated following the periodic evaluation (Reporting Period 1) of the TURNkey project by the EC.

In TURNkey, research is conducted in seismology, earthquake engineering, risk assessment and social sciences. In seismology and earthquake engineering sciences, many initiatives already exist to define the rules for scientific data management:

- European Plate Observatory System (EPOS) is a pan-European research infrastructure for solid Earth science to support state-of-the-art cross-disciplinary research activity in all fields of Solid Earth Science and to foster a safe and sustainable society.
- The International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN) is a global organization, and its objective is to define a universal standard for distribution of seismological waveform data and related parametric information. The Standard for Exchange of Earthquake Data (SEED) format is the result of that effort.
- The European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA) is an initiative within ORFEUS and is a distributed federation of datacenters established to securely archive seismic waveform data and metadata gathered by European research infrastructures, which follows the FDSN recommendation, and provides transparent access to data for the geosciences research communities.
- Additional European infrastructures for seismology (e.g., ORFEUS, EMSC) provide support for sharing and managing scientific data, and defining standards and rules applied to seismological data.

In conclusion, there is a long tradition of data sharing and openness in this field of research, to which most European projects (including TURNkey) adhere.

3 DATA SUMMARY

Quantitative and qualitative data will be generated and collected in line with the aims and objectives of the TURNkey project to help deliver a practical solution for OEF, EEW and RRE leading to more earthquake-resilient societies. The project will generate data relevant to the scientific community (researchers, institutions and organizations) and to different stakeholders (citizens, emergency/first responders, critical infrastructure owners and private/public business organizations). By providing these data it is anticipated that future utilization will contribute to the long-term success of the TURNkey project and enhance OEF/EEW/RRE advances across and amongst countries and organizations.

It is foreseen that four types of data will be collected: earthquake ground-motion data, geological, geophysical and earthquake engineering data (static data), stakeholder data and interpreted data.

3.1 Earthquake ground-motion data

3.1.1 TURNkey multi-sensor units

The number of instruments to be installed in the six physical TBs of the TURNkey project and the level of deployment is summarized in the table below.

Testbed			TURNkey multisensor units in Testbeds	
No.	Name	Country	RS4D	GNSS
TB1	Bucharest	Romania	15	5
TB2	Pyrenees	France	15	0
TB3	Hveragerði, Húsavík	Iceland	50	6
TB4	Patras and Aigio	Greece	40	9
TB5	Port Gioia Tauro	Italy	6	4
TB6	Groningen	Netherlands	6	2
Total			132	26

The estimated size of data collected from all the instruments (RS4D and GNSS) installed in the physical TBs of the project is:

- ~ 100 MB / RS4D / day -> with 132 RS4D = 13.5 GB /day
- ~ 100 kB / GNSS / day -> with 26 GNSS = 3 MB /day

Assuming that the instruments are running for about 1.5 years, this sums up to a total data volume of ~ 7.3 TB.

The new data generated by the project will be referenced through DOIs following the current practice in seismology, referencing the TURNkey project, and will be open access through the European Infrastructure for Data Access (EIDA). Three of the TURNkey TB leaders (INFP, NOA, KNMI) are running EIDA nodes, each of them will host its own TB data plus the data from an "adopted" TB:

- TB1 will host its own data + TB5 data
- TB4 will host its own data + TB3 data
- TB6 will host its own data + TB2 data

Formats of new data will follow the EIDA data structure, based on international standards for seismological data. It consists of raw data (e.g., digital files of seismograms) recorded by seismological stations and associated metadata with geographical information on where the data are recorded, the description of the instruments and the description of the acquisition.

3.1.2 Existing Sensor Networks

Data from existing sensor networks (seismic stations, radon sensors, etc.) already installed in or close to the TBs and data from the LastQuake and EarthquakeNetwork apps (felt reports) will also be used in the project. Permanent or temporary seismological networks provide data, complying with rules and standards established by the seismological community in Europe or internationally. The storage of this data is the responsibility of station and network owners.

3.2 Geological, geophysical and earthquake engineering data (static data)

The other type of scientific data that will be used in the project can be grouped in different categories:

- Hazard data (hazard maps, hazard curves, faulting mechanisms, GMPEs, Vs30 maps, CPT, SPT, Vs Profiles, etc.)
- Exposure data (building portfolio, insured portfolio, socio-economic data, etc.)
- Vulnerability data (fragility models, functionality los models, etc.)

The data listed above are all publicly available in different European countries. TURNkey is also using the data produced by previous projects funded under European programmes (SERA for example).

3.3 Stakeholder data

A starting point of the TURNkey project is to identify the stakeholders' requirements and to establish a common understanding of how each stakeholder group (citizens, emergency responders, critical infrastructure (CI) providers and public/private sector businesses) will use EEW/OEF/RRE to better prepare for, and recover from, an earthquake. This means that it is important to better understand the role that each end-user stakeholder group has in community resilience and to identify/describe the complex inter-relationships (sociological, political, economic, technical etc.) between stakeholder actions (before and after an earthquake).

First, the needs relative to the development of the suggested technology will be tested by the local agencies (selected by NTC) amongst key categories of interest: citizens, civil protection, municipalities and emergency/first responders. A qualitative approach, using focus groups and in-depth interviews will be used in three TBs (Italy, Greece and Romania), which reflect the different socio-economic-cultural characteristics of different earthquake zones found in Europe. Then, once a mock-up or prototype of the TURNkey solution is available, it will be tested in the three TBs. The research objectives are mainly to determine the:

- perceived appeal and relevance of the solution
- advantages/disadvantages of the solution
- likelihood of using the solution
- suggestions for improvement

The data collected will be used to provide recommendations for further development of the TURNkey platform.

Then, ARU will conduct interviews of Critical Infrastructures (CI) owners and public/private sector businesses in different TBs of the project. Once the stakeholders are identified, the data that will be collected in the TBs will be submitted for ethics approval through the ethics panel of ARU.

The data collected through the interviews will be used to develop a stakeholder performance metrics and a map of the interrelationships among the different stakeholders.

3.4 Interpreted data

Interpreted data are the products of research activities conducted in the TURNkey project. Most of the results are made available through scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals with open access and this will continue.

In addition to scientific publications, the results are also presented in the deliverables of the project. The public deliverables of the project will be made accessible on the TURNkey website once approved by the EC after each Reporting Period.

4 FAIR DATA

4.1 Findable

Seismological data used in the TURNkey project will follow recommendations made by European infrastructures in earth sciences and seismology. These recommendations concern the description of the metadata that follows a strict and standard format: a rich and standard description of the data and metadata to be used and re-used persistently; a strict naming of the data; the registration of the data and metadata in a

searchable resource; identification of the metadata; a unique format for the raw data (format SEED from FDSN infrastructure). Following these principles, a DOI will be assigned to new datasets, supported by the data providers or the datacenter hosting these datasets.

A depository for scientific publications on the TURNkey website will allow the interpreted results to be easily findable.

Versions, Keywords and Digital Object Identifiers will be explored in principle to aid the applicability of data. Identification mechanisms will be used to improve the usability of the data within differing contexts.

4.2 Accessible

The experimental data will be stored in an official and persistent center (EIDA nodes). It will benefit from existing identification mechanisms.

Open access will be provided to all scientific publications in line with the guidance provided by the European Commission (obligation for open access to scientific publications in Horizon 2020). Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications (moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications);
- ensure open access to the deposited publication - via the repository - at the latest:
 - on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case;
- ensure open access - via the repository - to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms ["European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020"]
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action, the beneficiaries must:

- deposit in a research data repository (the European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA) will be used as a data repository) and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate - free of charge for any user - the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible;
- provide information - via the repository - about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and - where possible - provide the tools and instruments themselves). Generic software tools, including MS Office, will be predominantly used.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardized by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the DMP must contain the reasons for not giving access.

4.3 Interoperable

The data produced in the TURNkey project will be interoperable, that is it will allow data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc. because it adheres to standards for formats, compliant with available and open software applications. We will follow data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies specified by the seismological community and the publishers to make the data interoperable.

Text mining tools and methods will help external actors to extract common and relevant data. A glossary of terms will be collated by project partners. Data files will be saved in an easily reusable format, commonly used by the research community.

4.4 Re-use

All the data will be open after validation and quality control performed by the hosting data center. For publication, copyright rules will be followed for the use of the results produced by the TURNkey project. To have an external quality control of the results, peer-review journals will be prioritized for publication.

Data will be stored either on each institution's back-up server or on a separate data storage device that is kept in a secure and fireproof location, separate from the main data point. Data will be released no later than the publication of findings and within three years of project completion. Primary data will be securely retained, in an accessible format, for a minimum of five years after project completion.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Extra costs for making data FAIR are not foreseen in the TURNkey project. If a publisher offers an open-access version for a fee, within reasonable limits and without affecting the financial resources for the proper conduct of the project, this option may be considered, but at the initiative of each partner. Permanent storage of the recorded seismic data in the EIDA data repository will not result in extra costs. Also the results of the other types of data collected through the TURNkey platform and the social investigations will be presented in the project deliverables that will be publicly available. The project coordinator (NORSAR) will be responsible for reminding partners of the FAIR principles applied in the TURNkey project.

6 DATA SECURITY

This research project will be in accordance with the following principles:

- Avoid using personal data wherever possible;
- If the use of personal data is unavoidable, consider partially or fully anonymizing the information to obscure the identity of the individuals concerned;
- Use secure shared drives to store and access personal data and sensitive business information, ensuring that only those who need to use this information have access to it;
- Use remote access facilities to access personal data and sensitive business information on the central server instead of transporting it on mobile devices and portable media or using third party hosting services;
- Personal equipment (such as home PCs or personal USB sticks) or third-party hosting services (such as Google Mail) should not be used for high or medium risk personal data or business information;
- If email is used to send personal data or business information outside the host institute, it should be encrypted. If unencrypted personal data or business information is sent to another partner email account, it should be indicated in the email title that the email contains sensitive information so that the recipient can exercise caution about where they open it;

- High or medium risk personal data or business information should not be used in public places. Caution should be exercised to ensure that no unencrypted high or medium risk personal data or business information is downloaded to an insecure device;
- Consider the physical security of personal data or business information, for example use locked filing cabinets/cupboards for storage;
- In accordance with the GDPR, personal data processed for any purpose or purposes should not be kept for longer than necessary for that purpose or purposes.

7 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management and data privacy will be discussed among the TURNkey partners in a devoted task (Task 7.5). The Task will start in M29 (October 2021). This task has the purpose to deal with IPR related to knowledge and tools developed during the project and to resolve any issues that may arrive despite of granted licenses, by referring to institutional and general practice on the protection of intellectual property derived from research. The DMP will be updated before the end of the project with the outcomes of the IPR agreement reached by the TURNkey Consortium in Task 7.5.

8 ETHICAL ASPECTS

The TURNkey Consortium ensures compliance with the GDPR. The Ethics Requirements are addressed in the corresponding deliverables (D9.1, D9.2 and D9.3).